

A blind steganography approach for hiding privacy details in images of digital imaging and communications in medicine using QR code

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to hide patient's privacy details of digital imaging and communications in medicine (DICOM) files using the quick response (QR) code images with the same size using steganographic technique. The proposed method is based on the properties of the discrete cosine transform (DCT) of the DICOM images to embed a QR code image. The proposed method includes two parts: data embedding and extraction process. Moreover, the stego DICOM image could be blindly used to produce the embedded QR code image without the existence of the original DICOM image. The performances of proposed method were evaluated using the metrics of the peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), the structural similarity index (SSIM), the universal quality index (UQI), the correlation coefficient (R) and the bit error rate (BER) values. The experimental results scored a high PSNR after the embedding process by embedding a QR code image into the DICOM image with the same size.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digital imaging and communications in medicine (DICOM) is the standard medical imaging data format, which is most used for the exchanging, management and viewing of medical images, such as computerized tomography (CT) scans, magnetic resonance imaging tests (MRIs), and ultrasound images [1]. The DICOM format was developed and copyrighted by the National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA) [2], [3]. It has been broadly espoused by hospitals and is making inroads into smaller applications like labs and dentists' and doctors' offices. The DICOM frequently parsed and enables the integration between different devices and platforms which using the picture archiving and communication system (PACS) [4]–[8].

The medical information of patients must be protected from unauthorized access. Generally, the medical information security refers to the rules of security policies that strict ethics rights and privacy of the patient and must be concerned by entities. There are many widely used standards and tools for protecting personal medical information such as the ISO27799 (security management in health using ISO/IEC/27799) [9], cryptography and steganography techniques [10]–[13]. The ISO27799 is a standard which provides the security management guidelines for health organizations to protect medical information. Cryptography is a data protection using encryption provider which converts the medical information into unintelligible text

using secure key. Steganography can be defined as the use of a host (container) data to hide or embed a piece of information that is hidden directly in media content, in such a way that it is imperceptible to a human observer but can be detected/extracted easily with a computer [14], [15].

The quick response code is always abbreviated to QR code which is a barcode that is readable by an imaging device such as a camera and smartphones. The QR code system was originally invented and designed in 1994 by the Japanese Company Denso Wave and it was registered as a trademark of the same company [16], [17]. Simply, the QR code is a matrix code of two-dimensional barcodes and consists of black squares arranged in a square grid on a white background. Unlike the one-dimensional barcodes that were designed to be scanned by a narrow beam of light, the QR code is scanned by a digital image sensor and then digitally analyzed by a programmed processor. The QR code includes three main distinct squares at the corners to set up the image size normalization, orientation, and angle of viewing. Moreover, the small dots throughout the QR code are then converted to binary numbers and validated with the Reed–Solomon error-correcting algorithm [18] which are encoded as bytes of 8 bits. In practice, QR codes often contain data for a locator, identifier, or tracker that points to a standard URL for a website or application. A QR code uses four standardized encoding modes (numeric-Max. 7,089 characters, alphanumeric- Max. 4,296 characters, byte/binary-Max. 2,953 characters, and kanji-Max. 1,817 characters) to store the amount of data efficiently; extensions may also be used [18].

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents the used materials and methods. The proposed method is illustrated in detail in section 3. Section 4 shows the experimental results and discussions. Finally, the study and the main contributions are concluded in section 5.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. The cancer imaging archive (TCIA) COVID-19 dataset

This study aims to hide patient's privacy details of DICOM files using the QR code images therefore, TCIA COVID-19 dataset is used [19]–[22]. TCIA COVID-19 dataset is a chest radiology imaging with CT imaging studies, a set of clinical data and key radiology findings for patients representing a rural COVID-19 positive population in the state of Arkansas. These data are cross-linked to severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) complimentary DNA (cDNA) sequence data extracted from clinical isolates from the same population, uploaded to the GenBank repository. This collection dataset includes 105 patient's data with 31,935 total number of images, 256 number of studies, 461 number of series and 19.0 GB images size. The TCIA COVID-19 dataset provides three study modality computed radiography (CR): (26 images (0.1%), 19 patients), direct digital capture (DX): (236 images (0.7%), 100 patients) and computed tomography (CT): (31673 images (99.2%), 23 patients). In addition, the dataset provides different images size between 350×552 to 3366×3006 using DICOM standard format. Figure 1 shows image samples description of the TCIA COVID-19 dataset.

Figure 1. DICOM images samples of TCIA COVID-19 dataset

2.2. The QR code

In this paper, the QR Code generator is based on the zebra crossing (ZXing) library [23]–[25]. The QR code generator is a software that creates data into a QR code image using the format information of two things: the error correction level and the mask pattern used for the symbol. The mask patterns are specified on a grid that is repeated as necessary to cover the whole symbol and protected from errors with a Bose-Chaudhuri–Hocquenghem (BCH) code and a double of complete copies are included in each QR pattern. Hence, ZXing is an open-source library project implemented in Java, with ports to other languages which supports generating and decoding of multi-format 1D/2D barcode image processing such as QR code and data matrix within images and all files can be imported on the fly from a maven repository or can be downloaded via a command. Figure 2 shows the generated four QR codes of various size which are used as an embedded image within the DICOM files.

Figure 2. QR code examples of various size and corresponding decoded text

3. THE PROPOSED METHOD

Figure 3 shows a high-level overall view of the main parts of the proposed method to embed patient information into the DICOM image. The main idea of this method is to generate a new image (stego) whose pixels are combination of two images with the same size where one of them is used as cover and the other is the secret message (Msg). The generated stego image should be similar to the cover image with little distortion as possible. Then this stego image could be blindly used to produce the embedded message without the existence of the original image. The proposed method includes two parts: data embedding and extraction process.

3.1. Data embedding process

In this process, the data embedding process mainly focuses on embedding the QR code image into the DICOM image. The proposed method collects patient information from the DICOM file and the corresponding clinical data such as patient ID, image study description, study modality and radiologist key findings. Next, the proposed method generates a QR code image using the collected patient data then it resizes the QR code image to be compatible with the cover DICOM image. As a preprocessing stage, both the QR code image and the cover DICOM image are normalized and adjusted to get float pixel values whose pixels have float values that belong to the interval [0, 1] instead of the integer range and to avoid an overflow in the embedded stego coefficients of saturated pixel values (0 or 1) using a small value (α) respectively.

$$\text{Normalization}(Img) = \frac{Img - \text{Min}(Img)}{\text{max}(Img) - \text{Min}(Img)} \quad (1)$$

$$Adjustment(Img) = \begin{cases} 1 - \alpha, & Img \geq 1 \\ \alpha, & Img = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

After normalization and adjustment are done, in preprocessing stage, the resultant cover and QR code images are divided into small parts of 4×4 matrices called micro-blocks (MB). Then the embedding process stage is ready to start.

In the embedding process, the main aim of this step is to embed the normalized MB of the QR code image into the corresponding normalized MB of the cover DICOM image to construct integrated stego DICOM image. Thus, 2-D discrete cosine transform (DCT) is applied on the cover's MBs.

$$DCT \text{ coefficients} = T \times MB_{Cover} \times T' \quad (3)$$

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{3\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{5\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{7\pi}{8}) \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{3\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{5\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{7\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{9\pi}{8}) \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{5\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{7\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{9\pi}{8}) & \sqrt{\frac{2}{4}} \cos(\frac{11\pi}{8}) \end{bmatrix}$$

The resultant matrix consists of 4×4 coefficients; one approximation and fifteen details coefficients. Next, the embedding process is carried out on the cover DCT coefficients by replacing these coefficients with the corresponding normalized QR code image's MB pixel values using (4).

$$Stego \text{ coefficient} = sign(DCT \text{ coefficient}_{Cover}) \left[\frac{2}{\beta} (MB_{QR \text{ code}} + i), \frac{2i}{\beta} \leq |DCT \text{ coefficient}_{Cover}| \leq \frac{2(i+1)}{\beta} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\forall i = 0,1,2, \dots, \beta - 1$$

Figure 3. A high-level overall view of the proposed method to embed patient information into DICOM image

The absolute values of the DCT coefficients lies in the interval [0, 2] where the range is actually determined by the minimum and maximum for each coefficient value Thus, β is an additional parameter that will be used to divide the range [0, 2] of the absolute value of the cover DCT coefficients. To improve stego image quality against noise, the approximation coefficient value of the cover image is kept without modification during the embedding process for each MB. After the embedding process is done, the stego DICOM image is obtained by applying the inverse DCT (Inv. DCT) then denormalization is applied to convert the pixel values back to their original domain using (5).

$$MB_{Stego} = T' \times DCT_{Stego} \text{ coefficients} \times T \quad (5)$$

Finally, the resultant stego image is saved as a medical image in DICOM format.

3.2. Data extraction process

The steps of extraction process are exactly the inverse of those followed during the embedding phases. Therefore, these process starts by read the stego DICOM image then apply the normalization to convert the pixel values to [0, 1] domain. Next, the normalized stego DICOM image is divided into 4×4 MB and compute the DCT decomposition using (6).

$$DCT \text{ coefficients} = T \times MB_{Stego} \times T' \quad (6)$$

After that, the extraction stage is applied on the stego DCT coefficients:

$$MB_{Rec-QR \text{ code}} = \frac{\beta}{2} \left(DCT \text{ coefficient}_{Stego} - \frac{2i}{\beta} \right), \frac{2i}{\beta} \leq |DCT \text{ coefficient}_{Stego}| \leq \frac{2(i+1)}{\beta} \quad (7)$$

$$\forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \beta - 1$$

where β is the same integer number is used in the embedding stage. In addition, to correctly reconstruct the first element in $MB_{Rec-QR \text{ code}}$, the mean value of three neighbors is calculated and replaced on it. Finally, the resultant *Rec-QR code* is denormalized to set the pixel values back to their original domain which is similar to the original QR code image.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses and analysis the results of the proposed method using the TCIA COVID-19 dataset, which was obtained from [19]–[22] that includes 105 patient's data with 31,935 total number of images, 256 number of studies, 461 number of series and 19.0 GB images size. The simulation was implemented using MATLAB version: 9.3.0.713579 (R2017b) with the image processing toolbox and includes read DICOM image function for image importing and conversion.

Figure 4 shows the DICOM image, QR code image, stego DICOM and reconstructed QR code image samples from two patients' TCIA COVID-19 images of the proposed method. Figures 4(a) to (d) illustrate the cover DICOM and the QR code images respectively however Figures 4(e) and 4(f) show the resultant stego DICOM image after embedding the QR code image into the cover DICOM image. Moreover, Figures 4(g) and 4(h) show the reconstructed QR code image after applying the extraction process from stego DICOM images by an authorized person. The simple visual inspection of the results shows a very high quality of the stego DICOM images while providing a scannable visual quality for the retrieved QR code image.

The performances of proposed method were evaluated using the peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), the structural similarity index (SSIM), the universal quality index (UQI), and the correlation coefficient (R) values, whose details were explained:

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{peakval^2}{MSE} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \left(f(x_i, y_j) - g(x_i, y_j) \right)^2$$

where $f(x, y)$ and $g(x, y)$ defined the cover and stego patients' images. M and N are the height and width of the images. The peakval is the range of the image data type (e.g., for uint16 image it is 65535). Figure 5

shows the resultant mean of PSNR values to compare between cover and stego DICOM images in decibel (dB). The mean PSNR values ranged between 63.47 dB and 81.97 dB for various values of β . The minimum and maximum value of the mean PSNR are 50.41 dB and 95.33 dB respectively. Generally, PSNR higher values refers that the invisibility of higher quality.

Figure 4. DICOM images samples of COVID-19-AR-16406494 and COVID-19-AR-16406561 and the results DICOM images of the proposed data hiding method: (a) to (d) illustrate the cover DICOM and the QR code images respectively, (e) and (f) the resultant stego DICOM image after embedding the QR code image into the cover DICOM image, (g) and (h) the reconstructed QR code image

The PSNR is approach to human observation of invisibility quality with the human visual system (HVS). On the other hand, the structural similarity (SSIM) index is a perceptual metric that quantifies image quality degradation as perceived change in structural information [26], [27]. In addition, the universal image quality index (UQI) proposed by Wang and Bovik evaluates the loss of correlation, luminance distortion, and contrast distortion [28], [29]. Therefore, the performances of SSIM and UQI are better than the MSE and PSNR. Equations (9) and (10) illustrate the SSIM and the UQI in details:

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y+c_1)(2\sigma_{xy}+c_2)}{(\mu_x^2+\mu_y^2+c_1)(\sigma_x^2+\sigma_y^2+c_2)} \quad (9)$$

$$UQI(x, y) = \frac{(4\mu_x\mu_y2\sigma_{xy})}{(\mu_x^2+\mu_y^2)(\sigma_x^2+\sigma_y^2)} \quad (10)$$

where μ_x and μ_y are the local means, σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 are the variance of x and y . σ_{xy} is the cross-covariance for images x , y . c_1 and c_2 are variables to stabilize the division with weak denominator. The correlation coefficient (R) is widely used in statistical analysis to compare two images in image processing purposes [30]–[33]. Equation (11) describes R in detail:

$$R = \frac{\sum_x \sum_y (f_{xy} - \bar{f}) - (g_{xy} - \bar{g})}{\sqrt{(\sum_x \sum_y (f_{xy} - \bar{f})^2)(\sum_x \sum_y (g_{xy} - \bar{g})^2)}} \tag{11}$$

where \bar{f} and \bar{g} are the mean of cover and stego patients' images pixels. Figure 6 shows the mean of the obtained SSIM to compare between the cover and resultant stego images. The minimum and maximum mean values of the SSIM confined between 0.979 and 1 while the overall mean SSIM values between 0.9964 and 1. Figure 7 and Figure 8 illustrate the obtained results of the mean UQI and the mean R respectively. The minimum and maximum values of the mean UQI are ranged between 0.48 and 1 while the minimum and maximum values of the mean R are recorded between 0.93 and 1. From the obtained PSNR, SSIM, UQI and R results, the value of the parameter β always effects on the resultant quality of the stego patients' image where the high β values produce high quality stego DICOM image.

Figure 5. The mean of resultant PSNR for stego and cover patients' DICOM images

Figure 6. The mean of resultant SSIM for stego and cover patients' DICOM images

Figure 7. The mean of resultant UQI for stego and cover patients' DICOM images

Figure 8. The mean of resultant R for stego and cover patients' DICOM images

Finally, the bit error rate (BER), returned as a scalar which is the number of bit errors to the total number of bits used in the binary representation. Figure 9 shows the mean BER between the cover and stego patients' DICOM images for various values of β . The mean BER values ranged between 0.1632 and 0.2820. The minimum and maximum values of the mean BER are 0.03 and 0.34 respectively.

Figure 9. The mean of resultant BER for stego and cover patients' DICOM images

5. CONCLUSION

Most DICOM objects contain images and associated demographic and medical information about the patient, which need to be kept confidential. Cryptography and steganography are generally used to ensure medical information of patients' security. Therefore, this study aims to hide patient's privacy details of DICOM files using the QR code images. Different sized 31,935 images of 105 patients were used as cover and embedded QR code images. The main idea of this method is to generate a new image (stego) whose pixels are combination of two images with the same size where one of them is used as cover and the other is the secret message (Msg). The generated stego image should be similar to the cover image with little distortion as possible. Then this stego image could be blindly used to produce the embedded message without the existence of the original image. The performances of proposed method were evaluated using PSNR, SSIM, UQI, R and BER metrics. The mean PSNR values ranged between 63.47 dB and 81.97 dB.

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